

NOTES

insoluble in ethanol readily separates. This has been purified and identified through analysis and undepressed melting point of a mixture with an authentic sample. Amine exchange is also easy with a 5-chloro substituent on the aromatic ring of the aldehyde moiety. But when X = H, the reaction is rather slow and a large excess of the bidentate amine had to be added so as to obtain a reasonable yield of the copper(II) complex of the quadridentate Schiff base.

The copper(II) complexes of tridentate, dibasic Schiff bases are known to be dimeric and antiferromagnetic⁶, and are known to give in pyridine (py) monomeric square planar [Cu(Py)(SB)]⁷. The interesting feature of the amine exchange reactions described herein (procedure A) is that in the starting Schiff base complex we have one hydroxyaldehyde moiety per copper(II) whereas in the final product we have two hydroxyaldehyde moieties per copper(II). This means that the two NH₂ groups of 'en' or 'tn' have to attack two azomethine carbon atoms of two tridentate Schiff base units. If we assume a long trans planar disposition of the two hydroxyaldehyde moieties of the starting dimeric species it is certain that the 'en' or 'tn' NH₂s can not simultaneously bite the two widely separated trans azomethine carbon atoms. Instead it appears more likely and less strenuous for the 'en' or 'tn' NH₂s to bite one azomethine carbon resulting in the destruction of the dimer and this is then followed by the other NH₂ end of 'en' or 'tn' biting a second neighbouring azomethine carbon in solution. That this suggestion has some appeal is revealed from the following considerations. On coordination to a copper(II) the azomethine carbon becomes positive (δ^+) making it more susceptible to a nucleophilic attack by NH₂ group of 'en' or 'tn'. In the free ligand also the azomethine carbon is expected to be distinctly though slightly positive because of electronegativity difference between carbon and nitrogen. It has been observed earlier^{4,8} that coordination is not the sole criterion for the polarisation of the azomethine carbon atom. In keeping with this we have observed a facile amine exchange on the Schiff

base alone when B is N = C—C₆H₅ and X is 5,6 benzo. Since in this case there is neither a metal complex involved nor any antiferromagnetic dimeric species the nucleophile does not have to resort to trans biting. The ready and facile amine exchange in the case of the free ligand indicates a similar path for the copper(II) complex also. In the complex surely the nucleophilic attack will be even more facilitated because the azomethine carbon becomes more positive due to coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to copper(II)⁸.

In conclusion we would like to note that synthesis of mixed chelates of the type [Cu(en)(SB)] or [Cu(tn)(SB)] via (a) reaction of 'en' or 'tn' with [Cu(SB)]₂ or via (b) reaction of [Cu(en)aq] or [Cu(tn)₂] with SBH₂ will remain a remote possibility.

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and D. DE. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 62.

2. R. L. DUTTA and S. P. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 497.
 3. H. S. VERTER and A. E. FROST, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 85.
 4. Y. MUTO, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1955, 76, 252; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 17559f.
 5(a) E. J. OLSZEWSKI and D. F. MARTIN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, 27, 345.
 (b) E. J. OLSZEWSKI and D. F. MARTIN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, 27, 1043.
 6. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR. and A. CHAKRABORTY; in 'Progress in Inorganic Chemistry', (Ed), F. A. Cotton, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1966, Vol. 7, p. 159.
 7. M. KUBO, S. KURODA, M. KISHITA and Y. MUTO, *Austr. J. Chem.*, 1963, 16, 7.
 8. D. F. MARTIN in 'Preparative Inorganic Reactions', (Ed), W. L. Jolly, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1964, Vol. 1, p. 65.

Thermodynamic Functions of F₂SNF, F₂SNCl and F₂SNBr from Spectroscopic Data

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THE extent of the reactivities of molecules may be ascertained from the knowledge of the thermodynamic functions of the molecules; the importance of ideal gas thermodynamic functions to equilibrium and kinetic phenomena is well known. It is almost impossible to obtain the thermodynamic properties of the electronically excited molecules and also some of the compounds in the ground state by experimental means, specifically in non-equilibrium situations, depending upon the range of temperature and pressure. Hence, only through theoretical calculations may one obtain information regarding the properties of these species. For such quantum statistical calculations, the vibrational and rotational data are needed, which at present can only be obtained from spectroscopic studies. Recently, the compounds, F₂SNF, F₂SNCl and F₂SNBr were prepared and their vibrational spectra have been reported in the literature¹. The assignment of the inplane and out-of-plane vibrations has also been made. Since these types of compounds are very difficult to prepare, thermodynamic functions of such compounds may not be determined easily by experimental means. Hence we thought it worthwhile to compute the thermodynamic functions of these molecules from the

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spectroscopic data The structural parameters of these molecules were taken from the literature¹

The statistical thermodynamic functions such as the enthalpy function, Gibbs energy function, entropy, and heat capacity were calculated for these molecules for the temperature range 100°–1500°K The values of moments of inertia used in our calculations of thermodynamic properties are given in Table 1 A

TABLE 1—MOMENTS OF INERTIA OF THE VARIOUS MOLECULES
(in a.u. Å²)

Molecule	Ia	Ib	Ic
F ₂ SNF	73 18	135 31	158 53
F ₂ SNCl	81 10	229 06	232 50
F ₂ SNBr	85 01	372 41	373 07

TABLE 2B—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF F₂SNBr
(in cal deg⁻¹ mole⁻¹)

T°K	C _p ^o	-(G°-H ₀ ^o)/T	(H°-H ₀ ^o)/T	S°
100 00	9 97	52 65	6 68	61 33
200 00	13 90	59 14	10 29	69 43
273 15	16 35	62 54	11 60	74 14
298 15	17 03	63 57	12 03	75 60
300 00	17 07	63 65	12 06	75 71
400 00	19 10	67 35	13 58	80 91
500 00	22 40	70 50	14 83	85 33
600 00	21 26	73 30	15 83	89 13
700 00	21 85	75 81	16 65	92 46
800 00	22 26	78 08	17 33	95 41
900 00	22 56	80 15	17 89	98 04
1000 00	22 78	82 06	18 37	100 43
1100 00	22 96	83 83	18 78	102 61
1200 00	23 09	85 48	19 14	104 62
1300 00	23 19	87 03	19 44	106 47
1400 00	23 28	88 48	19 72	108 20
1500 00	23 25	89 85	19 96	109 81

TABLE 2A—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF F₂SNF AND F₂SNCl
(in cal deg⁻¹ mole⁻¹)

T°K	C _p ^o	-(G°-H ₀ ^o)/T	(H°-H ₀ ^o)/T	S°
100 00	9 32 (9 68)	49 06(50 60)	8 30 (8 50)	57 36 (59 10)
200 00	12 79(13 46)	55 22(56 92)	9 66(10 01)	64 88 (66 93)
273 15	15 27(15 95)	58 41(60 23)	10 84(11 28)	69 25 (71 51)
298 15	16 01(16 66)	59 37(61 24)	11 24(11 70)	70 61 (71 94)
300 00	16 06(16 71)	59 44(61 31)	11 27(11 73)	70 71 (73 04)
400 00	18 35(18 85)	62 90(64 90)	12 78(13 26)	75 68 (78 16)
500 00	19 86(20 23)	65 89(68 01)	14 05(14 53)	79 94 (82 54)
600 00	20 86(21 15)	68 55(70 75)	15 11(15 56)	83 66 (86 31)
700 00	21 54(21 75)	70 95(73 21)	15 98(16 40)	86 93 (89 61)
800 00	22 02(22 19)	73 13(74 45)	16 71(17 10)	89 84 (92 55)
900 00	22 37(22 50)	75 14(77 50)	17 32(17 68)	92 46 (95 18)
1000 00	22 63(22 74)	76 99(79 39)	17 84(18 18)	94 83 (97 57)
1100 00	22 83(22 92)	78 72(81 14)	18 28(18 60)	97 00 (99 74)
1200 00	22 98(23 06)	80 32(82 78)	18 67(18 97)	98 99(101 75)
1300 00	23 10(23 17)	81 83(84 31)	19 01(19 29)	100 84(103 60)
1400 00	23 20(23 26)	83 25(85 75)	19 30(19 57)	102 55(105 52)
1500 00	23 28(23 33)	84 59(87 11)	19 56(19 82)	104 15(106 93)

The quantities within the brackets are for F₂SnCl

rigid rotator harmonic oscillator, independent-internal rotator approximation was used and all the quantities were calculated for the thermodynamic gaseous state of unit fugacity Also, assumed in the calculations were a symmetry number of one, singlet ground electronic state and chemical atomic masses The calculated values of the four thermodynamic quantities for these molecules are given in Table 2a and 2b

Comparison of the calculated values of the various thermodynamic functions with experimental data of these compounds is not reported since these are not available in the literature

Reference

1 R KEEBACIOGLU, R MEWS and O GLEISER, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1972, 28A, 1593